

**SIMPLIFICATION ON DYNAMIC RANGE OF A GENERALIZED
CHINESE REMAINDER THEOREM FOR MULTIPLE INTEGERS**

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Abstract

Motivated by multiple frequency determination in multiple undersampled waveforms, a generalization of the Chinese remainder theorem for multiple integers has been of recent interest. Liao and Xia (2007) obtained a lower bound on the dynamic range of multiple integers for their unique recovery. In this paper, we present a simplified bound with a simplified proof.

1. Introduction

The Chinese remainder theorem (CRT) tells us that a single nonnegative integer can be reconstructed from its remainders modulo several pairwise coprime moduli if and

only if the integer is less than the product of all the moduli. This ability to represent a large integer as a list of small residues or remainders leads to applications in numerous areas, such as cryptography, channel coding, and digital signal processing [4, 9].

There are various generalizations of the CRT; see [1–3, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12–14, 16] for some of them. In [12], motivated by multiple frequency detection from multiple undersampled rates, Xia presented the following generalized CRT problem for multiple integers.

Let $\gamma \geq 2$ and m_1, \dots, m_γ be γ pairwise coprime integers with $1 < m_1 < \dots < m_\gamma$ and let $\mathcal{N} = \{N_1, \dots, N_\rho\}$ be a set of ρ different nonnegative integers. For each $r \in \{1, \dots, \gamma\}$, define the r -th residue set of \mathcal{N}

$$S_r(\mathcal{N}) = \bigcup_{l=1}^{\rho} \{k_{l,r}\}, \tag{1}$$

where $k_{l,r}$ is the remainder of N_l modulo m_r .

The generalized CRT problem for multiple integers is to reconstruct the set \mathcal{N} from its residue sets $S_r(\mathcal{N})$, $1 \leq r \leq \gamma$. Note that it is unknown which element in \mathcal{N} produces a given element in $S_r(\mathcal{N})$ for any r . Moreover, $|S_r(\mathcal{N})|$ may be strictly less than ρ for some r , since two or more integers in \mathcal{N} may produce the same residue in $S_r(\mathcal{N})$. We use $|\cdot|$ to denote the cardinality of a set.

A basic question for the generalized CRT is to determine the *dynamic range* for the unique recovery. In what follows, we use \mathcal{M} and $S(\mathcal{N})$ to denote the sets $\{m_1, \dots, m_\gamma\}$ and $S_1(\mathcal{N}) \times \dots \times S_\gamma(\mathcal{N})$, respectively.

Definition 1. The dynamic range of \mathcal{M} , denoted $D_\rho(\mathcal{M})$, is the minimal positive integer D such that there exist two different ρ -subsets $\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{N}'$ of $\{0, \dots, D\}$ satisfying $S(\mathcal{N}) = S(\mathcal{N}')$.

Equivalently, the dynamic range $D_\rho(\mathcal{M})$ is the largest positive integer D such that the mapping

$$y = S(\mathcal{N}), \mathcal{N} \subseteq \{0, 1, \dots, D - 1\} \text{ and } |\mathcal{N}| = \rho$$

is invertible. For example, $D_1(\mathcal{M}) = \prod_{r=1}^{\gamma} m_r$ by the conventional Chinese remainder theorem. However, due to the unknown correspondence between \mathcal{N} and $S_r(\mathcal{N})$ for any $r \in \{1, \dots, \gamma\}$, the dynamic range for $\rho > 1$ seems extremely difficult.

Example 1. Let $\gamma = 4$, $\mathcal{M} = \{5, 7, 11, 13\}$, $\rho = 3$, $\mathcal{N} = \{13, 22, 35\}$ and $\mathcal{N}' = \{0, 13, 22\}$. One can check that $S(\mathcal{N}) = S(\mathcal{N}') = \{0, 2, 3\} \times \{0, 1, 6\} \times \{0, 2\} \times \{0, 9\}$. As \mathcal{N} and \mathcal{N}' are two different 3-subsets of $\{0, 1, \dots, 35\}$, the minimality of $D_3(\mathcal{M})$ implies $D_3(\mathcal{M}) \leq 35$.

The following basic lower bound on $D_\rho(\mathcal{M})$ was obtained by Xia [12]. For a set \mathcal{S} , we use $\max \mathcal{S}$ (resp. $\min \mathcal{S}$) to denote the maximum (resp. minimum) value of \mathcal{S} .

Proposition 1. [12] *We have*

$$D_\rho(\mathcal{M}) \geq \max \left\{ \prod_{r=1}^{\lfloor \frac{\rho}{2} \rfloor} m_r, m_\gamma \right\}. \tag{2}$$

The lower bound was improved further in [7]. To state their result, we need some notation.

Definition 2. An (ordered) ρ -partition of \mathcal{M} is a sequence of (possibly empty) subsets, $\mathcal{M}_1, \dots, \mathcal{M}_\rho$ of \mathcal{M} , denoted $(\mathcal{M}_1, \dots, \mathcal{M}_\rho)$, such that each m_r belongs to one and only one of these subsets.

Following [7], we define

$$b(\rho) = \max_{(\mathcal{M}_1, \dots, \mathcal{M}_\rho)} \min_{1 \leq l \leq \rho} \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}_l} m_r \tag{3}$$

and

$$c(\rho) = \min_{(\mathcal{M}_1, \dots, \mathcal{M}_\rho)} \max_{1 \leq l \leq \rho} \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}_l} m_r, \tag{4}$$

where the outermost maximum of (3) and the minimum of (4) are taken over all ρ -partitions $(\mathcal{M}_1, \dots, \mathcal{M}_\rho)$ of \mathcal{M} , and $\prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}_l} m_r = 1$ if $\mathcal{M}_l = \emptyset$.

The main result of Liao and Xia [7] can now be stated as follows:

Proposition 2. [7] *We have*

$$D_2(\mathcal{M}) \geq \max \{b(2), m_\gamma\} \tag{5}$$

and for $\rho \geq 3$,

$$D_\rho(\mathcal{M}) \geq \max \left\{ \min \{c(\rho), b(2)\}, \prod_{r=1}^{\lceil \frac{\rho}{2} \rceil} m_r, m_\gamma \right\}. \tag{6}$$

The goal of this paper is to show that the right-hand side of (6) is simply $c(\rho)$. Moreover, this leads to a simpler proof of (6). We remark that the exact dynamic range for two integers ($\rho = 2$) was obtained recently in [11], by extending a key idea in [15].

2. Simplification of (6)

We begin with bounds on $b(\rho)$ and $c(\rho)$ obtained in [7].

Lemma 1. [7] Let $\rho \geq 2$. We have

- (i) $b(\rho) \leq \left(\prod_{r=1}^{\gamma} m_r\right)^{\frac{1}{\rho}}$ and
- (ii) $c(\rho) \geq \max \left\{ \prod_{r=1}^{\lceil \frac{\rho}{2} \rceil} m_r, m_{\gamma} \right\}$.

Lemma 2. Let $\rho \geq 3$. If

$$\prod_{r=1}^{\gamma-1} m_r < m_{\gamma} \tag{7}$$

then $b(2) < c(\rho) = m_{\gamma}$; otherwise, $c(\rho) \leq b(2)$.

Proof. Assume (7) holds. Let

$$(\mathcal{M}_1, \mathcal{M}_2, \dots, \mathcal{M}_{\rho}) = (\{m_1, \dots, m_{\gamma-1}\}, \{m_{\gamma}\}, \emptyset, \dots, \emptyset). \tag{8}$$

Then, by (7), we have

$$\max_{1 \leq l \leq \rho} \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}_l} m_r = \max \left\{ \prod_{r=1}^{\gamma-1} m_r, m_{\gamma}, 1, \dots, 1 \right\} = m_{\gamma}, \tag{9}$$

which implies $c(\rho) \leq m_{\gamma}$ by the minimality of $c(\rho)$. On the other hand, by Lemma 1 (ii), $c(\rho) \geq m_{\gamma}$. This proves $c(\rho) = m_{\gamma}$.

Now by Lemma 1 (i) and (7),

$$b(2) \leq \left(\prod_{r=1}^{\gamma} m_r\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} < m_{\gamma}. \tag{10}$$

This completes the proof of the first half.

Next, we assume

$$\prod_{r=1}^{\gamma-1} m_r \geq m_{\gamma}. \tag{11}$$

Let $(\mathcal{M}_1, \mathcal{M}_2) = (\{m_1, \dots, m_{\gamma-1}\}, \{m_{\gamma}\})$. Then, by (11),

$$\min_{1 \leq l \leq 2} \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}_l} m_r = \min \left\{ \prod_{r=1}^{\gamma-1} m_r, m_{\gamma} \right\} = m_{\gamma}. \tag{12}$$

This, by the maximality of $b(2)$, implies

$$b(2) \geq m_{\gamma}. \tag{13}$$

Let $(\mathcal{M}'_1, \mathcal{M}'_2)$ be a bipartition of \mathcal{M} such that

$$b(2) = \min \left\{ \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_1} m_r, \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_2} m_r \right\}. \tag{14}$$

Without loss of generality, we may assume

$$b(2) = \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_1} m_r, \tag{15}$$

i.e., $\prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_1} m_r \leq \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_2} m_r$. Note that the inequality is necessarily strict since m_1, \dots, m_γ are pairwise coprime. Thus,

$$\prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_1} m_r < \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_2} m_r. \tag{16}$$

From (13), (15) and (16), we have

$$\prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_2} m_r > m_\gamma \tag{17}$$

and hence $|\mathcal{M}'_2| \geq 2$ since m_γ is the largest modulus in \mathcal{M} .

Now let $(\mathcal{M}'_{2,1}, \mathcal{M}'_{2,2})$ be any bipartition of \mathcal{M}'_2 with $\mathcal{M}'_{2,i} \neq \emptyset$ for $i = 1, 2$. We claim

$$\prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_{2,i}} m_r \leq \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_1} m_r \text{ for } i = 1, 2. \tag{18}$$

Suppose to the contrary that (18) does not hold, say,

$$\prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_{2,1}} m_r > \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_1} m_r. \tag{19}$$

Then we consider a new bipartition of \mathcal{M} :

$$(\mathcal{M}''_1, \mathcal{M}''_2) = (\mathcal{M}'_1 \cup \mathcal{M}'_{2,2}, \mathcal{M}'_{2,1}). \tag{20}$$

As $\mathcal{M}'_{2,2} \neq \emptyset$, we have

$$\prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}''_1} m_r > \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_1} m_r. \tag{21}$$

Combining (19) with (21) leads to

$$\min \left\{ \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}''_1} m_r, \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}''_2} m_r \right\} > \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_1} m_r \tag{22}$$

and hence $b(2) > \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_1} m_r$ by the maximality of $b(2)$. This is a contradiction to (15) and hence (18) is proved.

Now, as $\rho \geq 3$, we can define

$$(\mathcal{M}_1^*, \mathcal{M}_2^*, \dots, \mathcal{M}_\rho^*) = (\mathcal{M}'_1, \mathcal{M}'_{2,1}, \mathcal{M}'_{2,2}, \emptyset, \dots, \emptyset), \tag{23}$$

where the last $\rho - 3$ (possibly zero) parts are all empty sets. By (18), we have

$$\max_{1 \leq l \leq \rho} \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}_l^*} m_r = \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_1} m_r \tag{24}$$

and hence $c(\rho) \leq \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}'_1} m_r$ by the minimality of $c(\rho)$. This implies $c(\rho) \leq b(2)$ by (15) and hence finishes the proof of this lemma. \square

Now, we can give a simplification for the right-hand side of (6).

Theorem 1. *For $\rho \geq 3$, we have*

$$\max \left\{ \min \{c(\rho), b(2)\}, \prod_{r=1}^{\lceil \frac{\gamma}{\rho} \rceil} m_r, m_\gamma \right\} = c(\rho). \tag{25}$$

Proof. We consider two cases according to Lemma 2 as follows.

If (7) holds, then $b(2) < m_\gamma$. Clearly, $\lceil \frac{\gamma}{\rho} \rceil \leq \gamma - 1$ and hence by (7),

$$\prod_{r=1}^{\lceil \frac{\gamma}{\rho} \rceil} m_r \leq \prod_{r=1}^{\gamma-1} m_r < m_\gamma. \tag{26}$$

Thus, the left-hand side of (25) is equal to m_γ . Note in this case, $m_\gamma = c(\rho)$ by Lemma 2. Thus, (25) holds.

If (7) does not hold, then $c(\rho) \leq b(2)$. Now, (25) clearly follows by Lemma 1 (ii). \square

3. A Simple Proof of (6)

We begin with a simple but crucial lemma, whose proof can be regarded as a refinement of that used in [12].

Lemma 3. *Let $N \in \{0, \dots, c(\rho) - 1\}$ and $\mathcal{N} = \{N_1, \dots, N_\rho\} \subseteq \{0, \dots, c(\rho) - 1\}$. If $N \bmod m_r \in S_r(\mathcal{N})$ for each $r \in \{1, \dots, \gamma\}$, then $N \in \mathcal{N}$.*

Proof. For each $l \in \{1, \dots, \rho\}$, we define the set

$$\mathcal{A}_l = \{m_r : N \equiv N_l \bmod m_r\}. \tag{27}$$

For each m_r , since $N \bmod m_r \in S_r(\mathcal{N})$, there exists at least one $l \in \{1, \dots, \rho\}$ such that $N \equiv N_l \pmod{m_r}$, i.e., $m_r \in \mathcal{A}_l$. Therefore, $\bigcup_{l=1}^{\rho} \mathcal{A}_l = \mathcal{M}$. In order to form a ρ -partition of \mathcal{M} , we define

$$\mathcal{M}_l = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^l \mathcal{A}_i \right) - \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{l-1} \mathcal{A}_i \right) \tag{28}$$

for $l = 1, \dots, \rho$, where the empty union $\bigcup_{i=1}^0 \mathcal{A}_i$ is defined as the empty set. Clearly, $(\mathcal{M}_1, \dots, \mathcal{M}_\rho)$ is a ρ -partition of \mathcal{M} and $\mathcal{M}_l \subseteq \mathcal{A}_l$. Let \mathcal{M}_{l^*} be the one in $\mathcal{M}_1, \dots, \mathcal{M}_\rho$ such that the product of all $m_r \in \mathcal{M}_{l^*}$ is the maximum, i.e.,

$$\prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}_{l^*}} m_r = \max_{1 \leq l \leq \rho} \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}_l} m_r. \tag{29}$$

Hence, by the minimality of $c(\rho)$,

$$c(\rho) \leq \prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}_{l^*}} m_r. \tag{30}$$

It suffices to show $N = N_{l^*}$. As $\mathcal{M}_{l^*} \subseteq \mathcal{A}_{l^*}$, the definition of \mathcal{A}_{l^*} implies

$$N \equiv N_{l^*} \pmod{m_r} \text{ for } m_r \in \mathcal{M}_{l^*}. \tag{31}$$

By (30) and the assumption of this lemma, we see that both N and N_{l^*} are less than $\prod_{m_r \in \mathcal{M}_{l^*}} m_r$. Therefore, the conventional CRT implies $N = N_{l^*}$ from (31). \square

Now, we can give a proof of (6). We rewrite (6) as follows by Theorem 1.

Theorem 2. *For $\rho \geq 3$, we have*

$$D_\rho(\mathcal{M}) \geq c(\rho). \tag{32}$$

Proof. It follows from Definition 1 that $D_\rho(\mathcal{M}) \geq \rho$. Thus, if $c(\rho) \leq \rho$ then (32) holds. Therefore, we may assume $c(\rho) > \rho$. Let \mathcal{N} and \mathcal{N}' be any two ρ -subsets of $\{0, 1, \dots, c(\rho) - 1\}$ satisfying $S_r(\mathcal{N}') = S_r(\mathcal{N})$ for each $r \in \{1, \dots, \gamma\}$. It suffices to show $\mathcal{N}' = \mathcal{N}$.

Let $N' \in \mathcal{N}'$. Then $0 \leq N' < c(\rho)$ and $N' \bmod m_r \in S_r(\mathcal{N}') = S_r(\mathcal{N})$. By Lemma 3, we obtain that $N' \in \mathcal{N}$ and hence $\mathcal{N}' \subseteq \mathcal{N}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{N} \subseteq \mathcal{N}'$ and hence $\mathcal{N}' = \mathcal{N}$, as desired. \square

We remark that the equality in (32) may hold for some special cases. Consider Example 1. Clearly, $c(3) = 5 \times 7 = 35$ and hence $D_3(\mathcal{M}) \geq 35$. Recalling $D_3(\mathcal{M}) \leq 35$ in Example 1, we have $D_3(\mathcal{M}) = 35$.

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